

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

METHODOLOGY OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE ACTIVITIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract

Motivation to master English and the desire to improve oneself, the movement to improve one's speech culture; and communicative competencies in intercultural communication are personal results of students, which are formed when learning a foreign language. Thus, for students to achieve the above-mentioned personal results, the teacher must choose and select educational tasks to foster feelings of benevolence, responsiveness, and empathy for other people, and these tasks stimulate aesthetic needs and feelings.

Keywords: *set time limits, the ability to control, implies the ability to compare the method of action, the ability to correct.*

The methodology of the formation of communicative activities in English lessons, which are aimed at increasing the developmental potential of education as the main element, determines the activities that are developed based on the systemic activity approach. Learning activities are an invariant foundation of educational and upbringing processes, helping to realize the possibility of independent qualitative assimilation of new knowledge and skills of students based on the formation of the competence of the ability to learn.

The theoretical and methodological basis for the development of the level of complete general education within the organization of work of the state standards of general education of the second generation is the cultural-historical and system-activity approaches, which were developed in the works of scientists L. S. Vygotsky, V. V. Davydov, P. Y. Galperin, A. N. Leontiev and others, which reveals the leading psychological provisions and mechanisms of the process of assimilation of knowledge, formation of worldview, the general structure of learning activities of students.

The principles of age-appropriateness of training are theoretically confirmed and are reflected in 2 main doctrines:

1) L.S. Vygotsky's doctrine of the structure and dynamics of psychological age;

2) the doctrine of periodization of mental development of students, which determines the main age-related psychological regularities of personality development and cognition process. The main results of the process of education and upbringing, defining them in terms, rely on the content of psychological new-formations of students. In the development of communicative activities in English lessons, four groups are distinguished:

1) personal. Actions, which provide functioning of life, personal, and professional self-determination; a sense of education, and moral and ethical evaluation, which are realized based on the value-sense orientation of students, besides the ability to orient in social roles, as well as interpersonal relations.

2) regulative. These are actions that allow students to organize their learning activity as an activity aimed at self-education; goal-setting is the setting of both learning tasks and cognitive tasks; the ability to plan means determining the order of intermediate goals and tasks, taking into account the final results; the ability to make a plan and determine the sequence of actions;

the ability to predict is the ability to anticipate the result and level of learning, to set time limits; the ability to control implies the ability to compare the method of action and its result with a specific standard to timely detect deviations and differences from the standard; the ability to correct, i.e. to make necessary additions and corrections to the plan and ways of action, if there are discrepancies and differences from the standard, the present action and its result; the ability to evaluate implies the ability to distinguish and realize what has already been learned and what is yet to be learned, the ability to realize the quality and level of the learned material.

3) cognitive. Cognitive actions cover general learning actions, including sign-symbolic, logical, and problem-solving actions. The significance of general learning actions is in the management of cognitive processes. General learning actions can include:

a) exploratory (e.g., independent definition and independent formulation of a cognitive goal, hypothesis, and carrying out the verification of the truth of the hypothesis),

b) informational (e.g., searching for and selecting necessary data, including using computer technologies, familiarization with methods and techniques of processing, storing, protecting and using information),

c) sign-symbolic (e.g., substitution, creation, and transformation of a model to identify general regularities that define a given subject area, application of a model to solve various problems).

4) communicative activities organize and regulate interaction and cooperation of students with other people, in addition, they perform the function of exteriorization (according to A.N. Leontiev and P.Y. Galperin,

the formation of forms of mental activity occurs through the restructuring of external subject activity into internal mental activity. Communicative activities in English lessons provide social competence and help to take into account the positions of students, teachers, parents and other people, companionship in communication or activity, the ability to listen and dialogue, to take an active part in a joint discussion, the ability to join a group and build effective interaction and productive cooperation of students with other adults. Communicative activities consist of:

1) detailed planning of educational interaction of students. It is necessary to define the purpose, and functions of the participants of interaction and ways of interaction;

2) formulation of questions - active interaction in searching and collecting information;

3) resolving conflict situations. It is necessary to identify and carry out problem identification, search for and evaluate alternative methods of conflict resolution, decision making and its implementation;

4) managing the interlocutor's behavior. It is necessary to carry out control and corrective actions, to be able to evaluate the actions of a partner. It is necessary to form the ability to express one's thoughts accurately according to the tasks and conditions of communication;

5) active mastery of various forms of speech (monologue and dialogic) according to the grammatical and syntactic norms of the language. We would like to note that in the process of learning English the formation of all types of communicative activities can be called the main goal of learning a foreign language. The process of learning English is aimed at the development and formation of the communicative competence of students, which would give them a chance to successfully solve communicative tasks in various situations of communication. Formation of communicative activities takes place in all kinds of speech activity: speaking, listening, writing, and reading. When planning practical activities of students during the lesson, it is necessary to take into account the differentiation of students following the level of preparation and the pace of work. The teacher selects tasks that allow any student to create a situation of success. Thus, while in a traditional lesson frontal work is often used, in an individual lesson individual, pair, and group work prevails. Working in pairs and groups is necessary for students to learn to cooperate, to be ready to interact, and to be able to distribute roles, i.e. teenagers develop communicative skills, which was mentioned above. Group work is used quite well when creating various projects.

During the training of self-control and self-assessment skills, the students develop regulatory and communicative actions. Pedagogical technologies that exist, for example, cooperative learning, project method, application of new IT technologies, and Internet opportunities in teaching help to organize the learning process by the personality-oriented approach in teaching, as well as help to build the learning process taking into account the individual characteristics of students and use methods of differential learning, taking into account the level of learning of students, the level of

available abilities, as well as the aptitudes of each student, etc.

Motivation to master English and the desire to improve oneself; the movement to improve one's speech culture; and communicative competencies in intercultural communication are personal results of students, form when learning a foreign language. Thus, for students to achieve the above-mentioned personal results, the teacher must choose and select educational tasks to foster feelings of benevolence, responsiveness, and empathy for other people, and these tasks stimulate aesthetic needs and feelings. The students like festive events very much, and they play etiquette monologues and greetings with great desire: 'Happy Teacher's Day', and 'Nauryz'. They try to learn and memorize forms of gratitude and start to use them later in appropriate speech situations, thank you a lot, thank you very much. The ability to master the subject of "English" independently and successfully, encompassing the independent organization of this process, i.e. the ability to learn, is guaranteed by the fact that communicative activities reveal to him 'the chance of a broad orientation both in various subject areas and in the structure of the learning activity itself, which includes awareness of its target direction, value and meaning characteristics, and national'.

Thus, we see that to teach English it is necessary to form and develop communicative skills of students in the practical mastery of English. It is communicative activities that ensure the ability to express their thoughts, which are related to the communicative task, to build a dialogue and listen, to take into account the points of view of interlocutors in the dialogue, to take an active part in the general consideration of issues, to learn to interact in a group of peers and build a productive dialogue and productive cooperation with classmates, teachers, and parents.

As follows from the above, the formation of monologue speech is one of the directions of mastering communicative activity by a student. Monologue speech is understood as a time-spanning presentation of a system of thoughts, and knowledge by one speaker. Monologue speech has the characteristics of coherence, contextually of speech, as well as consistency, proof of presentation, and grammatical correctness of sentence construction. The forms of monologue speech include:

1) report, 2) lecture, 3) speech, 4) story.

It should be noted that monologue speech always involves interaction with the audience, as it requires thorough preparation. In speech psychology and the science of psycholinguistics under monologue speech is understood as a coherent speech of one speaker, its communicative task is to communicate to listeners any facts, or information about the phenomena of real life'.

. According to L.G. Shadrina, monologue speech is one of the most complex forms of speech, which serves to convey information with a specific purpose. The main properties of monologue speech are listed below:

a) the nature of the utterance is one-sided and continuous;

b) the message is arbitrary, extended, and logically consistent, its content is conditioned by its orientation towards the listener;

c) non-verbal means of transmitting information are used to a limited extent.

Monologue speech is a special type of organization of speech activity, its difference from other types of speech activity is related to the specificity of speech functions. Monologue speech uses and generalizes the following elements of the language system: vocabulary, methods of expressing grammatical relations, form and word-forming, and various syntactic means. Besides, in it, the idea of a judgment is implemented, which is stated sequentially, coherently, and planned. The implementation of a coherent extended statement implies that a person keeps in his memory a program drawn up for the entire length of the speech message, during the presentation, all kinds of control over speech activity, the core of which is auditory and visual perception. If we compare monologue speech with dialogic speech, it can be noted that monologue speech is characterized by greater contextually and the narration has a more complete form, with logical means and the various syntactic constructions used to be carefully selected.

The main characteristics of monologue speech include:

- *consistency*;
- *logicality*;
- *completeness*;
- *coherence of the presentation*;
- *compositional design*.

All these characteristics originate from the contextual and continuous form. The coherence of speech is the main condition of communicative speech activity, regardless of its form. In order to master this most important aspect of speech, it is recommended that learners develop special skills of composing statements with the reliance on their coherence. Psychological and pedagogical sources identify the following main criteria for determining the coherence of an oral utterance:

a) *the presence of semantic links between the chapters of the story*;

b) *the presence of logical and grammatical connections between sentences*;

c) *the presence of connections between words in a sentence*;

d) *the presence of completeness in the expression of the speaker's thought*.

The second most important characteristic of an extended statement is the sequence of presentation. If the sequence of presentation is broken, it can negatively affect the coherence of the whole text. The logical and semantic organization of a monologue largely determines the observance of its coherence and sequence. Mastering the skills of the logical and semantic organization of an utterance contributes to a clear, planned presentation of thought, i.e. arbitrary and conscious implementation of speech activity. When carrying out speech activity, a person follows the 'internal logic', revealing the whole structure of subject relations.

An elementary manifestation of a semantic connection is an inter-phrase connection reflecting the relationship between two concepts. Monologue speech activity fulfills the following communicative functions: - informative. Its essence consists in the communication of new material in the form of knowledge about objects and phenomena of the world around us, the transfer of events, actions, and states with the help of words; - influencing. It convinces the interlocutor of the truth of certain thoughts, views, beliefs, and actions. This function induces action or prevents it; - emotional-evaluative. It implies the presence of evaluative statements about events, objects, phenomena, and actions. Each of the above functions of monologue speech is characterized by its linguistic means of expression and special psychological incentives.

Based on the main communicative functions of monologue speech, it is accepted to speak about its functional types:

1) monologue-description is a way of presenting thoughts. When presenting information, the subject, and phenomena are described in a static state. The description implies the enumeration of the main qualities of the subject/appearance, distinctive features, and characteristic features. The following blocks are available in the structure of a descriptive monologue:

- a) an introduction,
- b) the central part,
- c) conclusion or ending.

Distinctive features of the monologue-description:

- the presence of a large number of qualitative and descriptive adjectives;
- the presence of a clear and precise scheme of the statement (the beginning - the main part - the ending);
- the use of complex sentences in speech (provided that the level of English is sufficient);
- sentences complicated by descriptive appendages, mode of action appendages, and homogeneous sentence members.

Monologue description can be presented as a description (characteristic) of a country, city, district, neighborhood, school, historical event, event in the country, description of the properties of a substance, device, machine, scheme, drawing, etc.

2) monologue-narrative (or narrative, story), in which information is reported about developing events and states; The construction of a monologue-narrative can be defined by the following sequence: beginning; main part; conclusion (conclusion).

3) monologue - reasoning. This type of speech activity is characterized by a special logical connection between the judgments that form an inference. The construction of the monologue-reasoning plan is a unity of the following elements: thesis; evidence; and conclusion.

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